

**BASIC THEORETICAL PROBLEMS OF PHRASEOLOGY IN MODERN
LINGUISTICS DEFINITION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS, THEIR
SEMANTIC FEATURES, HISTORY OF PU RESEARCH**

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Annotation

This work is devoted to the study of phraseological units of adjectives of taste in the English and Russian linguistic picture of the world. The Relevance of the work is due to the growing interest of linguists in phraseological semantics, to the problem of the phraseological picture of the world in connection with the importance of identifying similarities and differences in different languages. The problems of comparative phraseology attract the attention of many linguists.

Key words: academic words, phraseological units, morphology, lexicology, adjectives of taste, semantic features.

Phraseology is a branch of the science of language, the object of study of which is stable combinations of words - phraseological units (PU). The founder of the theory of phraseology is Charles Bally, a Swiss linguist of French origin. He understood this science as "studying connected combinations". Also Sh. Bally gave the following definition of a phraseological unit: "combinations that have become part of the language are called phraseological phrases" [Kunin 1996: 5]. In the book "Essays on Stylistics" S. Bally identified four types of phrases: 1) free phrases 2) familiar combinations 3) phraseological series 4) phraseological unity. Later, in the book "French stylistics", he indicated two groups of combinations: free combinations and phraseological unity. The work done by him contributed to the further development of phraseological research [Ibid p. 5].

In the English and American linguistic literature, works devoted to the theory of phraseology are few. "Therefore, in the English language there is no generally accepted term for this discipline" [Ibid. with. nine].

English and American linguists who study stable word combinations use the term "idiom" to denote phraseological units. The term "idiom" was first introduced by the English linguist L.P. Smith. In his work "Phraseology of the English language" he used the word "idiom" to denote such features of the language that are speech anomalies that violate either the rules of grammar or the laws of logic. He referred to idioms: phraseological combinations, grammatical phenomena - "double" expression of comparative and superlative

degree (more better), double negation, persistent repetitions of the same words (by and by, again and again, neck and neck) [Smith 1998].

The most common definition of an idiom belongs to W. McMordie and J. Seidl. They understand an idiom as “a series of words that invent a meaning other than the meanings of its components” [Seidl 1978: 4].

At the moment, linguists disagree on the definition of phraseological unit and the volume of phraseology. But, despite the divergence of opinions on the definition of phraseology, it was the Soviet linguists who defined and introduced the term "phraseological unit", denoting a special group of phrases. Currently, the issue of the volume of phraseology has not yet been resolved. “In modern philological science, a situation has been established in which the concept of phraseology is expanding. The volume of phraseology includes words, idioms, and compound terms, all kinds of stable syntactic constructions, proverbs, sayings, sayings, winged words and numerous stamps of oral and written speech” [Zalyaleeva 2003: 4].

According to A.V. Kunin's phraseological unit includes all “stable combinations of words with complicated semantics” from “two-conditional formations” to complex sentences, i.e. proverbs [Kunin 1996: 31]. E.V. Ivanova believes that, considering the issue of the boundaries of the phraseological fund, proverbs and phrasal verbs should be mentioned [Ivanova 2011]. However, A.I. Alekhina believes that phraseology includes stable verbal complexes of phraseological and non-phraseological nature [cit. according to Zagryadskaya 2003].

So, from all of the above, it is obvious that there are differences of opinion on the concept of "phraseological unit". In this work, we will adhere to the definition of A.V. Kunina: “A phraseological unit is a stable combination of words with a fully or partially rethought meaning” [Kunin 1996: 210].

List of used literature

1. Amosova N.N. Fundamentals of English phraseology / N.N. Amosova, L. : 1963 .-- 207 s.
2. Arutyunova N.D. The language and the world of man // languages of Russian culture M. : 1999. - 896 p.
3. Akhmanova O.S. Dictionary of linguistic terms. MSK. : publishing house "Soviet Encyclopedia" 1996. - 606 p.
4. Babushkin A.P. Types of concepts in lexico-phraseological semantics language, their personal and national specificity: diss. Dr. phil. Sciences: 02/10/19. Voronezh, 1997 .-- 330 p.

5. Boldyrev N.N. Cognitive semantics: a course of lectures in English philology // Ed. 2nd, TSU. Tambov, 2001 .-- 123 p.
6. Vinogradov V.V. Lexicology and lexicography: selected works / V.V. Vinogradov. M .: 1977 .-- 312 p.
7. Demyankov V.Z. Concept and concept in fiction and scientific language / Questions of philology / № 1 / V.Z. Demyankov. 2001.S. 26-33
8. Zalyaleeva A.R. English and Russian phraseological units with a "person" component: diss. Cand. Phil. Sciences: 10.02.20. Kazan, 2003 .—23 with.
9. Zagryadskaya N.A. Personal phraseological units and their place in English phraseology: diss. Cand. Phil. Sciences: 10.02.04. M .: 2003. -145 p.
10. Ivanova E.V. Lexicology and phraseology of modern English language // Textbook for students of institutions of higher vocational education // Grif UMO on classical university education. St. Petersburg: Faculty of Philology, St. Petersburg State University Publishing house "Academy", 2011. - 352 p.
11. Karasik V.I. Linguocultural conceptology / V.I. Karasik, N.A. Krasavsky. Volgograd: Paradigm, 2009 .-- 115 p.